

Ionic Association of Transition Metal Ions with Bicarbonate using Spectrophotometric Method. Part-I. Zinc and Manganese in Aqueous Media at Different Temperatures

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Manuscript received 17 November 1984, accepted 29 April 1985

Spectrophotometric measurements in the uv range of bicarbonate ion is used to obtain its stoichiometric association constants (K) with Zn and Mn metal ions. K values are obtained at various ionic strengths using NaClO_4 as ionic strength fixer. Using Davies equation in obtaining the activity coefficients, the thermodynamic association constant, K_A , was then obtained at each of the four temperatures 15, 25, 35 and 45°.

Also, ΔH° , ΔG° and ΔS° values are obtained. The results at 25° are compared to those obtained by other authors on the same salts using ion-selective electrode method. It is suggested then that this method can be used directly with some care of pH adjustment, in obtaining thermodynamic data of metal-bicarbonates.

METAL ligand ion pairs were shown to be geochemically significant in Garrels and Thompson's model of sea water¹. Garrels and Thompson showed that the MgHCO_3^+ and CaHCO_3^+ ion-pairs contributed significantly to the control and distribution of the carbonate species in sea water. However, when the validity of their model was checked with the experimental values² they concluded that more HCO_3^- is tied-up than could be accounted for by simply Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} complexation. Reasons for this could be the difficulty in determining accurate formation constants for the species of interest and the failure to consider all interactions. Indeed, a literature search^{3,4} proved that existing thermodynamic data for the MgHCO_3^+ and CaHCO_3^+ ion-pairs did not span a range of geochemically interesting temperatures in general.

We view the ocean as an equilibrium chemical system in equilibrium with the atmosphere. We then consider all of the major inorganic species in the ocean and their interactions as described by classical thermodynamics. This leads us to a set of the major chemical equilibria important in the ocean. Unlike normal laboratory situations, many of the oceanic equilibria are coupled together through common species. For example, the bicarbonate ion occurs as a reactant in five different equilibria, thereby 'coupling' these equilibria together. Our primary research objective is the

measurement of the thermodynamics of all the important sea water equilibria. Although we measure our thermodynamic data in 'pure' laboratory systems, the basic data obtained should be applicable to the complex ocean system.

In this study, we carried out spectrophotometric measurements in the uv range on some 2 : 1 salts which are very important in the oceanography, which are Zn and Mn bicarbonates. Our measurements serve several purposes, namely, study the ionic association of these salts as examples for 2 : 1 salt using this direct and simple technique. Secondly, to continue our study on the similar salts, Ca, Ni and Co bicarbonates which were carried out in our laboratory previously⁵. Unfortunately we could not carry out measurements at higher ionic strengths ($> 0.1 M$) to simulate the ocean conditions because the association under these conditions could not be detected easily. However, the results can be extended by combining the thermodynamic association constant (K_A) and the activity coefficients at the needed ionic strengths. Our measurements were carried out at different temperatures 25, 35 and 45°.

Experimental

Measurements were made using a Zeiss PMQ 2 spectrophotometer equipped with 1 cm cell. The temperature of the solution was maintained constant by circulating the cell compartment with water at

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fixed temperature from water-bath, controlled to $\pm 0.05^\circ$.

All stock solutions were prepared and stored in polyethylene bottles. The dilution was made freshly before running the spectra. The cells used in the experiment were matching 1 cm quartz cells. Series of solutions made of known fixed concentration of NaHCO_3 and known but different concentrations of $\text{Zn}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ or $\text{Mn}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$, were prepared.

All measurements were carried out at 225 nm wavelength. To fix ionic strength, sodium perchlorate solution was used for adjustment. Measurements were carried out at three ionic strengths 0.0012, 0.01 and 0.05 M, and at different temperatures 25, 35 and 45° .

It must be noted that before the preparation of bicarbonate solution, correction was done⁵. Since the carbonic acid is not completely dissociated, it is necessary to calculate the amount of bicarbonate formed according to equation (1),

$$K_a = 1.7 \times 10^{-4} = \frac{[\text{H}][\text{HCO}_3^-]}{[\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3]}$$

Results and Discussion

The reaction under investigation is represented by equation (2),

at start a b 0
at equilibrium a-x b-x x

where, M represents Zn or Mn, and S denotes the solvent used. Here we adjusted the experimental conditions to allow 1 : 1 ion-pair, *i.e.* monodentate rather than polydentate.

It can be shown⁵ mathematically that the stoichiometric association constant K be calculated using equation (3) by plotting ab/A vs $(a+b)$,

$$\frac{\text{ab}}{A} = \frac{1}{K\epsilon} + \frac{(a+b)}{\epsilon} \quad (3)$$

where, A is absorbance of Zn or Mn HCO_3^+ , ϵ is extinction coefficient, and K is stoichiometric association constant; and whose slope = $1/\epsilon$ and intercept = $1/K\epsilon$.

Thermodynamic association constant (K_A) can be calculated using equation (4),

$$K_A = \frac{K}{f_{\pm}(\text{M}^{2+})} \quad (4)$$

where, $f_{\pm}(\text{M}^{2+})$ is the mean activity coefficients of the corresponding species. Values of stoichiometric and thermodynamic association constants for ZnHCO_3^+ and MnHCO_3^+ at 25, 35 and 45° are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—STOICHIOMETRIC AND ASSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF ZnHCO_3^+ IN H_2O AT 25, 35 AND 45°

Temp. $^\circ\text{C}$	I M	K LM^{-1}	f_{\pm}	K_A LM^{-1}	Average K_A LM^{-1}
25	0.0012	23.36	0.8585	27.21	26.30 ± 1.0
	0.0100	18.15	0.6624	27.40	
	0.0500	11.53	0.4556	25.31	
35	0.0012	30.11	0.8585	35.07	34.80 ± 0.4
	0.0100	23.30	0.6624	35.18	
	0.0500	15.65	0.4556	34.35	
45	0.0012	36.74	0.8585	42.79	42.90 ± 0.1
	0.0100	28.50	0.6624	43.03	

TABLE 2—STOICHIOMETRIC AND ASSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF MnHCO_3^+ IN H_2O AT 25, 35 AND 45°

Temp. $^\circ\text{C}$	I M	K LM^{-1}	f_{\pm}	K_A LM^{-1}	Average K_A LM^{-1}
25	0.0012	18.36	0.8585	21.39	22.10 ± 0.7
	0.0100	15.07	0.6624	22.75	
	0.0500	10.09	0.4556	22.14	
35	0.0012	24.99	0.8585	29.10	30.70 ± 1.6
	0.0100	21.37	0.6624	32.30	
	0.0500	13.58	0.4556	29.80	
45	0.0012	34.05	0.8585	39.66	38.30 ± 1.3
	0.0100	24.51	0.6624	37.00	

Thermodynamic parameters ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° which were obtained for ZnHCO_3^+ and MnHCO_3^+ in this study are in good agreement with the results obtained by others^{6,7} as 25° as shown in Table 3.

TABLE 3—SUMMARY OF THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR ZnHCO_3^+ AND MnHCO_3^+ IN THIS WORK AND LITERATURE VALUES AT 25°

Technique	Salt	$-\Delta G^\circ$	ΔH°	ΔS°	$\log K_A$
		kcal mol ⁻¹			
Spectral*	ZnHCO_3^+	1.94	2.06	0.013	1.40
	MnHCO_3^+	1.81	2.19	0.013	1.32
Ion-selective electrode**	ZnHCO_3^+	1.91	0.85	0.009	1.40
	MnHCO_3^+	1.73	0.98	0.009	1.27

*This work. **Refs. 6 and 7.

In all cases studied, ΔH° values are found to be positive indicating that heat must be added to reactants for the equilibrium to take place in forming the ion-pairs. It is clear that the association of MnHCO_3^+ is more endothermic than that of ZnHCO_3^+ in pure aqueous media. Also, it is worth noting that these systems were never studied using the simple spectrophotometric technique before. The fact that the results obtained from this technique are in excellent agreement with those obtained by I.S.E. method, encouraged us to use the spectral method for other bicarbonates relevant to oceanography. These measurements are currently under investigation and the preliminary results are very encouraging.

One important and good feature for the spectrophotometric method over others is that it can be used under high pressures, which are highly needed for deep sea simulations.

References

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